

The 8-Theory in a Nutshell

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Abstract:

By analyzing the framework from a general point of view, it is possible to get a sense of the entire scope, the predictions, the main ideas and how they relate to each other. The equations, their simplicity and power of prediction with regard to the coupling constants magnitudes and to the masses.

Introduction

8 theory is describing a Lorentz manifold inside an Euler Lagrange equation:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} = 0 \quad (1)$$

The manifold will be stationary by requiring the last two terms:

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad - \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

If true, we have time invariant acceleration, away from extremums curving on the manifold. In agreement with our model of the universe. The major strength of the framework is predicting the value of the fine structure constant and the entire series of coupling Constants. One boson for each prime number.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (3)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (3.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1)$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ...$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

Other significant predictions 8-theory has is a prediction of families forming below first generation. Total mass of fourth family should stand at 0.113 Mev, 56 times lighter than the total mass of the first family. This prediction is also intersecting with the unanswered enigma of dark matter. We predict infinite Families with mass converging to zero.

We also predict the universe to be flat. By putting a manifold in Euler Lagrange equation we demand that all arbitrary variations of the manifold to vanish. Arbitrary variations are random amount of curvature on the manifold, and so, the underlining principle of nature in this framework is to eliminate the curvature. Elimination of arbitrary curvature is the Cause of matter creation.

Simplifications it contains relative to QFT are that in this framework, there is no need to insert operators of matter creation and destruction. Those things happen in quite natural sequence and can be summed in one term - δg . The framework does not have any spatial dimensions nor does it depend upon frames of reference.

Second simplification is the subject of description. This theory describe one entity – the Lorentz manifold. It does not describe particles or fields of any sort, their motion, momenta, energy, and trajectory, potential and so on. The theory is a mathematical skeleton, which revolves around manifold variation and not particle motion. In fact, the skeleton of the theory is almost purely mathematical; it has no physical constants other than the coupling Constants, which were derived mathematically. Other subjects the 8-theory can elucidate is spin – representing the equation on the prime's critical line:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

We have no data on exact time in which the electron will emit a boson. Nor we have the direction of propagation. God Is playing with dices in this framework. Cosmological inflation is another subject we can shade a new light on. In this framework the inflation is the shift from a compressed Lorentz manifold, to an expended Lorentz manifold, to due asymmetry between the matter anti-matter causing the manifold to have A curvature, yielding an outward acceleration.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)